

FROM PLANS TO PLATFORMS: ENHANCING PARTICIPATORY URBAN PLANNING THROUGH TECHNOLOGY IN DAVAO CITY**Dr. Joel S. Pardillo**

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed on how technology influence urban planning in Davao City, Philippines. Using a mixed-methods approach, the research explored how key stakeholders currently use and view digital platforms on Geographic Information Systems (GIS), online permitting systems, and social media consultations. Data were gathered and collected through document reviews, surveys, and interviews with government officials, planning staff, and civil society members.

The results show that while awareness of digital tools is fairly high, regular engagement is low due to issues with usability, limited access, and inadequate training. The platforms received moderate scores for accessibility and relevance but were rated poorly for responsiveness and feedback. Despite these challenges, 90% of respondents said they would be more willing to engage if the tools were more user-friendly and accessible.

The findings highlight the need for a digital ecosystem that encourages participation, includes mobile-friendly features, provides real-time feedback channels, and offers support at the barangay level. The study concludes that having digital infrastructure alone is not enough. Ongoing community involvement, skill-building, and responsiveness from institutions are crucial for successful and inclusive urban planning. Recommendations include creating a technology adoption plan that emphasizes co-creation, digital literacy, and the long-term use of participatory tools.

INTRODUCTION

During the last few decades, cities across the globe have witnessed unprecedented growth fueled both by world population growth and rural-urban migration. The world population stood at approximately 8.2 billion in 2024 and is set to rise to 9.7 billion by 2050 before slowing down and stabilizing at the turn of the century (United Nations, 2022). Concurrently, the Philippines continues to be a high-growth country; its population is projected to grow from approximately 113.9 million in 2025 to 138.7 million by 2055 (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2021). Such fast-paced demographic growth imposes huge stress on urban systems—most prominently in rapidly expanding cities such as Davao.

Davao City exemplifies this phenomenon at the local level. From a population of just 392,000 in 1970, it surged to 1.78 million by 2020, growing at an annualized rate of 1.79% from 2015 to 2020 (PSA, 2021). Including surrounding areas, the metro population now nears 2 million and is projected to reach roughly 2.5 million by 2035 (City Planning and Development Office – Davao City, 2022). This population boom has reconfigured the cityscape: urban barangays now contain around 80% of citizens, from less than 60% in 2000 (City Planning and Development Office – Davao City, 2022), reflecting high urban migration and residential concentration.

This explosive urban growth has produced mixed results. On the positive side, Davao's economy is booming: it achieved a 7.5% GDP growth in 2023, surpassing other regions in Mindanao (PSA – Region XI, 2024). On the negative side, however, the city is now increasingly burdened by: insufficient public transportation, worsening traffic congestion, increased flooding brought about by wetland destruction, and the spread of informal settlements (Lacorte, 2023). Significantly, Davao lost 95% of its urban wetlands since the 1940s, leading to high flood hazards in quickly built settlements (Flores, 2021). To meet the challenges brought about by rapid urbanization, urban planners are now relying more on digital technology and data-based tools like Geographic

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Information Systems (GIS), smart infrastructure systems, and urban simulation models. These technologies provide invaluable insights for land use optimization, bettering transportation networks, and enhancing disaster resilience (Batty, 2018; Yeh, 2019). This study seeks to identify and evaluate such technologies appropriate for implementation in Davao City's urban planning. Finally, the results of this research will be disseminated to other Local Government Units (LGUs) in the Philippines to inform scalable, evidence-based urban planning interventions.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

While technology holds great promise for improving urban planning, its adoption within local government settings like Davao City remains uneven and faces several obstacles. This study explores the extent to which digital tools are currently being used in Davao City's planning processes. It investigates how these technologies contribute to greater efficiency, transparency, and stakeholder participation, while also identifying the key challenges and limitations in their implementation. Ultimately, the study aims to offer practical insights on how Davao City can strengthen its urban planning efforts through a more inclusive and effective digital transformation.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to examine how technology improves urban planning processes in Davao City. Specifically, it seeks to identify the current digital tools and platforms utilized in the city's planning processes and assess their effectiveness and usability in enhancing planning efficiency and outcomes. Furthermore, the study aims to evaluate the challenges encountered in the adoption and implementation of these planning technologies. Based on the findings, it intends to formulate and recommend a technology adoption plan to further improve and support the city's urban planning initiatives.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

This study adopts a mixed methods research design that combines both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a well-rounded understanding of the role of digital tools in urban planning.

Multiple data collection methods will be used to ensure depth and breadth in analysis. A document review will be conducted to analyze key materials such as urban development plans, zoning ordinances, and outputs from digital platforms like Geographic Information Systems (GIS), online zoning tools, and electronic permit systems. Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) will be carried out with individuals directly involved in the planning process, including city planners, IT personnel, GIS specialists, and technology partners, to gather expert insights on system implementation and performance. To capture a broader perspective, surveys and questionnaires will be distributed to planning staff and community stakeholders to assess their experiences, challenges, and perceptions regarding the use of digital tools. In addition, a case study approach will be used to examine specific initiatives such as the application of GIS or an online building permit system as concrete examples of technology's impact on planning processes.

Data analysis will be conducted in two parts: qualitative data from interviews and document reviews will be coded thematically to identify recurring patterns and insights, while quantitative data from surveys will be analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, and Likert scale averages. The research will take place in Davao City, Philippines, with a range of targeted respondents. Primary participants will include officials from the City Planning and Development Office (CPDO), zoning administrators, the Davao City GIS Unit, IT staff supporting planning platforms, and representatives from NEDA Region XI. Secondary participants will consist of barangay officials involved in planning, civil society organizations engaged in urban development, external technology vendors if applicable, and local residents and business owners who interact with digital planning services and can provide user feedback. This comprehensive methodology aims to uncover both the technical and human dimensions of Davao City's digital planning transformation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The survey consisted of 31 participants representing a range of sectors, including architecture, engineering, local government (city and barangay officials), business, and education. Participants were predominantly in their mid-20s to late 40s and held at least a bachelor's degree, with many reporting one to five years of experience in

urban development or planning-related processes. This demographic reflects a cross-section of individuals who are either directly involved in or significantly exposed to the planning landscape of Davao City.

The study found that Davao City has begun adopting several digital platforms to support its urban planning functions. According to survey results, 67.7% of respondents reported being aware of at least one digital tool currently utilized by the local government (Table 1). These tools include the Online Building Permit System, Zoning and Land Use Online Maps, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and social media-based consultations such as Facebook Live sessions and online surveys. Among these, social media consultations were the most recognized (54.8%), followed by the building permit system and zoning tools (each at 48.4%), and GIS (35.5%). The presence of these platforms reflects ongoing efforts to digitize planning processes and improve stakeholder communication, especially within the City Planning and Development Office (CPDO), GIS Unit, and allied agencies.

While the presence of these platforms' signals progress, their overall effectiveness remains mixed. Participants rated these tools as moderately useful in enhancing transparency, speeding up permit approvals, and visualizing land use data. However, usability was a recurring concern. Tools like GIS, while powerful, were noted to be less accessible to non-specialists due to their complexity. Conversely, social media platforms were considered more user-friendly and engaging, particularly for gathering public opinion (Figure 1).

Despite the utility of these tools, limited integration across platforms and lack of mobile responsiveness reduced their impact. Still, a large majority (90%) of respondents indicated they would be more willing to engage in planning activities if the digital systems were made easier to navigate and access.

The implementation of digital planning tools is hindered by several key challenges. First, low public awareness was identified by 64.5% of respondents as a significant barrier (Table 1). Second, there is a shortage of technical training for both government staff and the public, limiting their ability to fully utilize advanced systems such as GIS or e-permitting platforms. Third, infrastructure limitations, such as inconsistent internet access in barangay areas, impede wider participation. Institutional constraints, including budget limitations and resistance to change among some departments, also slow the digital transformation. These challenges reflect a disconnect between the availability of technology and its meaningful use in participatory planning.

In light of these findings, a technology adoption plan should prioritize capacity-building, platform accessibility, and institutional alignment. First, the city should conduct regular training programs on digital tools for both planning staff and community stakeholders. Second, platforms should be designed with a mobile-first approach, ensuring usability for citizens who primarily access the internet via smartphones. Third, establishing real-time feedback loops, such as chatbots or messaging-based reporting, would increase responsiveness. Fourth, integrating systems (e.g., linking GIS data with zoning platforms and permits) could streamline processes and improve data accuracy. Finally, empowering barangay-level offices with the digital infrastructure and skills to act as local planning nodes would promote inclusivity and decentralized participation.

Table 1.0 Awareness and Challenges in Digital Tools and Platforms

Indicators	Rating	Significance
Awareness on Digital Tools and Platforms	67.7% - High Awareness	Awareness of digital tools and platforms in urban planning is essential for promoting participatory governance, efficient decision-making, and the effective use of technology on managing urban growth. It reflects the readiness of stakeholders to engage with modern planning process and supports the implementation of data-driven solutions

Legend: 100% - 81% - Very High Awareness, 80% - 61% - High Awareness, 60% - 41% - Moderate Awareness, 40% - 21% - Low Awareness, 20% - 0% - Very Low Awareness

Indicators	Result	Significance
Challenges in the Adoption and Implementation	64.5% - Low Awareness of Platform	The identification of low awareness by 64.5% of respondents highlights a major barrier to the effective use of urban planning platforms. This indicates the need for improved information dissemination and capacity-building to maximize the platforms impact on planning process.

Figure 1.0 Public Preferences of Urban Planning Engagement Methods

CONCLUSION

The integration of digital tools in urban planning offers Davao City an opportunity to modernize its processes while deepening citizen engagement. Although platforms like GIS and online permitting exist, they remain underutilized due to low awareness, limited training, and a lack of participatory design. Survey findings confirm the need for an inclusive, accessible, and responsive digital ecosystem to support planning transparency and collaboration.

The findings emphasized that digital infrastructure alone is not enough. Without proper outreach, capacity-building, and institutional responsiveness, these tools risk becoming underused systems that fail to address the real needs of the public. The challenge lies not only in making technology available but ensuring it is meaningful, equitable, and accessible to all sectors of society.

A people-centered smart city is not only defined by its infrastructure but also by how it empowers its citizens to shape their environment. Going beyond top-down implementation to create platforms that promote two-way communication, build trust, and reflect local context. Digital tools must be embedded in a governance framework that values openness, co-creation, and sustained community. Through strategic investment in digital tools and institutional reforms, the city can unlock a more inclusive planning process that reflects the voices of its citizens.

Moreover, integrating participatory digital planning into long-term development strategies can help the city become more resilient, adaptive, and responsive to future urban challenges, such as rapid growth, climate change, and socioeconomic inequality.

When planning is collaborative and data-informed, resources can be better allocated, policies become more relevant, and communities feel more invested in the outcomes.

In doing so, Davao City can set a national precedent- not just as a technologically advanced city, but as a truly participatory and inclusive one. The path forward calls for leadership, cross-sector collaboration, and a sustainable commitment to bridging the digital divide, ensuring that no citizen is left behind in the planning of their city

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